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ORIGINAL ARTICLE

A Regularized Trefftz Method for Solving an Inverse Problem for the Laplace Equation

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ABSTRACT

The present paper proposes a new regularised Trefftz method to recover the boundary value on a non-accessible boundary of an annulus from overdetermined data on the accessible boundary of that annulus. Considering that the available data have a Fourier expansion, we consider the Tikhonov damping factor in constructing our regularized scheme, which satisfies the boundary value problem. At the same time, the convergence estimates for the regularised solution will be established under an assumption for the exact solution. The finite term truncation of the series expansion allows us to match the boundary condition as accurately as desired. By the collocation method, we derive a system of linear equations that can be uniquely solved to obtain the coefficients and preset the regularisation parameter and the damping factor to ensure adequate stability. The numerical efficiency of the proposed method is investigated with a high truncation number in comparison with the modified collocation Trefftz method.

INTRODUCTION

The mixed problem of Laplace equation in plane domain is a classical one, has its origins in the experimental sciences, and occurs in several physical and engineering applications [1]. Although for some simple and doubly-connected domains with contour like as circle, ellipse, annulus, the Laplace equation has at most one exact solution [2-4]. Many results about the existence, uniqueness and regularity of solution to the Boundary value problem for the Laplacian was presented [5-10].

In experimental situations, when boundary conditions are partially or entirely unknown that cannot be evaluated because of physical difficulties or geometric inaccessibility, then an inverse problem must be formulated to reconstruct the missing data on the inaccessible part of the boundary of the domain considered, so-called, data completion problem which are generally ill-posed problems in Hadamard's sense [10]. This kind of problems has a great importance and can be considered as a challenge in many fields of industry, such as, the electrostatic, fluid mechanics, geophysics, medical imaging, structural mechanics, non-destructive testing of structure [11], elastic bending beam [12].

The study of flow through an annular region defined by two coaxial pipes has found considerable practical application in many fields such as chemical production and processes, bio-medical, ecological engineering, physiology, petroleum, aerospace and processing industries [13,14]. In this paper we consider a mathematical modeling of a such problem and give an effective numerical algorithm for a method to detect the velocity in the annular space from a measurements of flow field on the accessible boundary.

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The Trefftz Method (TM) was developed since 1926, it has been widely studied and applied to many engineering problems. The main idea of this method is to extend the numerical solution in terms of T-complete functions that satisfy the governing equation. The TM is less popular than other numerical methods such as Finite Difference Method (FDM), Finite Element Method (FEM), Boundary Element Method (BEM), etc., because the system of linear equations resulting from the Trefftz method is an ill-posed problem, even for a well-posed boundary value problem, also for multi-connected domains, the conventional TM fails [15,16].

Recently, Young, Chen and Kao have proposed the Modified Collocation Trefftz Method (MCTM), for solving the Laplace problems, that provide a very interest method which make converge the serie expansion of solution and decreased the condition number of discretization matrices, compared with the Collocation Trefftz Method (CTM) [3,16-18]. There are some tasks to recover boundary conditions for Laplace equation [4,10,19-23]. For the boundary reconstruction [14,21]. However, we find that errors do not decrease when the truncation numbers increase [17], which leads to significant errors with high truncation numbers.

Our starting point consist to modify the series expansion of the solution by entered the Tikhonov's damping factor to construct a new regularized scheme that satisfy the problem and make converge the series expansion of the regularized solution with an estimation of errors under exact and noisy data. The finite term truncation and the collocation were considered to approximate the solution, then the unknown coefficients can be determined by matching the boundary conditions. As long as, we can minimize the errors by increasing the truncation number that make the remainder of the series expansion of solution small as possible which provides a gain for this new method.

For the outline of this work, the section two contain the formulation of problem and some tools for our development. In section three, we examine the convergence of this new method and it's stability for noisy data. In section four, the finite term truncation and the collocation method were used to construct the new regularized collocation Trefftz method (NRCTM). Matching the boundary data renders a system of linear equations for the coefficients to be determined using the conjugate gradient method. Numerical examples are provided in section five to testing the NRCTM and compare it with the Modified Collocation Trefftz Method (MCTM), to show its feasibility.

Preliminaries and General Formulations

In this paper we consider a new regularized method to solve the inverse Cauchy problem of the Laplace equation in an annulus domain which is formulated by imposing the Dirichlet-Neumann data on the interior boundary:

$$\Delta u = u_{rr} + \frac{1}{r}u_r + \frac{1}{r^2}u_{\theta\theta} = 0 \tag{2.1}$$

$$u(R_0, \theta) = u_0(\theta), \quad 0 \leq \theta \leq 2\pi \tag{2.2}$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial n}(R_0, \theta) = u_1(\theta), \quad 0 \leq \theta \leq 2\pi \tag{2.3}$$

We assume that Γ_0 and Γ_1 are a circles with a radius R_0 and R_1 , respectively. The normal derivative is given as

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial n} \Big|_{r=R_0} = \frac{\partial u}{\partial r} - \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial u}{\partial \theta} \frac{\partial R_0}{\partial \theta} \Big|_{r=R_0} \tag{2.4}$$

by using formula

$$\nabla u = \frac{\partial u}{\partial r} e_r + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u}{\partial \theta} e_\theta, \quad n = e_r - \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial R_0}{\partial \theta} e_\theta$$

where, e_r and e_θ are the polar coordinates of the unit vectors [2].

We can replace Eqs. (2.2) by the following boundary conditions [17,23]

$$\begin{cases} u(R_0, \theta) = u_0(\theta), & 0 \leq \theta \leq 2\pi \\ u(R_1, \theta) = g(\theta), & 0 \leq \theta \leq 2\pi \end{cases} \tag{2.5}$$

where $g(\theta)$ is an unknown function assumed to be determined, then the Dirichlet data are completed on the whole boundary, in addition the solution of Laplace equation can be obtained in the whole domain. Therefore, we face the following inverse problem:

Inverse problem: Given the data Γ_0 , u_0 and u_1 , determine the function $g(\theta)$.

We assume that both functions $u_0(\theta)$ and $u_1(\theta)$ are L^2 integrable on the interval $[0, 2\pi]$. Hence, both of them admit development in terms of the Fourier expansion as:

$$u_0 = A_0 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} A_n \cos(n\theta) + B_n \sin(n\theta) \tag{2.6}$$

$$u_1 = A_0' + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} A_n' \cos(n\theta) + B_n' \sin(n\theta)$$

Applying the variable separation method, then the solution [2,19] of the equation (2.1) in the exterior of the circle of radius R_0 , is given as:

$$u(r, \theta) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (f_n(r) \cos(n\theta) + g_n(r) \sin(n\theta)) \tag{2.7}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} f_0(r) &= c_{0,1} + c_{0,2} \ln(r), & g_0(r) &= 0 \\ f_n(r) &= c_{n,1}r^{-n} + c_{n,2}r^n, & g_n(r) &= d_{n,1}r^{-n} + d_{n,2}r^n, \text{ pour } n \geq 1 \end{aligned} \tag{2.8}$$

and the coefficients $c_{n,1}, c_{n,2}, d_{n,1}, d_{n,2}$ are uniquely determined [8] by matching the boundaries condition (2.6) as:

$$\begin{aligned} c_{0,1} &= A_0 - A'_0 R_0 \ln R_0, & d_{0,1} &= 0 \\ c_{0,2} &= A'_0 R_0, & d_{0,2} &= 0 \\ c_{n,1} &= \frac{1}{2} A_n R_0^n - \frac{1}{2n} A'_n R_0^{n+1}, & d_{n,1} &= \frac{1}{2} B_n R_0^n - \frac{1}{2n} B'_n R_0^{n+1} \quad n \geq 1 \\ c_{n,2} &= \frac{1}{2} A_n R_0^{-n} + \frac{1}{2n} A'_n R_0^{1-n}, & d_{n,2} &= \frac{1}{2} B_n R_0^{-n} + \frac{1}{2n} B'_n R_0^{1-n} \quad n \geq 1 \end{aligned} \tag{2.9}$$

Definition 4.1 For $n \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{0\}$ the sequence

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}}, \quad \frac{\cos(n\theta)}{\sqrt{\pi}}, \quad \frac{\sin(n\theta)}{\sqrt{\pi}}, \dots \tag{2.10}$$

is a Hilbert basis for $L^2(0, 2\pi)$ and the following norm can be defined for $r > 0$ as

$$\|u(r, \cdot)\| = \|u(r, \cdot)\|_{L^2(0, 2\pi)} = \langle u, u \rangle^{\frac{1}{2}} = \left(\int_0^{2\pi} u(r, \theta)^2 d\theta \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \tag{2.11}$$

where, the function u is given by (2.7) and verify that

$$\|u(r, \cdot)\|^2 = 2\pi f_0(r)^2 + \pi \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (f_n(r)^2 + g_n(r)^2) \tag{2.12}$$

Regularization Method and Convergence Estimates

The main idea of the regularization problem is to approach the considered ill-posed problem by a family of well-posed problems depending on a (small) regularization parameter. As similar we consider the regularized problem associated to the ill-posed problem (2.1)-(2.2)-(2.3) with $\alpha > 0$ is the regularization parameter and δ is the noisy level resulting from the measurements of the given data u_0, u_1 , with condition [24,25]

$$\|u_0^\delta - u_0\| \leq \delta, \|u_1^\delta - u_1\| \leq \delta \tag{3.1}$$

In what follow we consider that u is the exact solution obtained from the exact data u_0, u_1 and u^δ the approximate solution obtained from the noisy data u_0^δ, u_1^δ . We note by u_α is the regularized solution associated to u_0, u_1 and u_α^δ is the regularized solution associated to u_0^δ, u_1^δ , thus the following regularized problem can be defined as

$$\Delta u_\alpha^\delta = 0, \tag{3.2}$$

$$u_\alpha^\delta = u_0^\delta, \quad 0 \leq \theta \leq 2\pi \tag{3.3}$$

$$\frac{\partial u_\alpha^\delta}{\partial n} = u_1^\delta, \quad 0 \leq \theta \leq 2\pi \tag{3.4}$$

From (2.6) and the property (3.1) then u_0^δ, u_1^δ are L^2 integrable on the interval $[0, 2\pi]$, then both have a fourier expansion as

$$\begin{aligned} u_0^\delta &= A_0^\delta + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} A_n^\delta \cos(n\theta) + B_n^\delta \sin(n\theta) \\ u_1^\delta &= A_0'^\delta + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} A_n'^\delta \cos(n\theta) + B_n'^\delta \sin(n\theta) \end{aligned} \tag{3.5}$$

We consider the suite of functions $q_n(\alpha, \mu)$, for $\alpha > 0$ and $0 < \mu < \infty$ defined by [23, 24]

$$q_n(\alpha, \mu) = \frac{\mu^{-2n}}{\alpha + \mu^{-2n}}, \forall n \in \mathbb{N} \tag{3.6}$$

which satisfy the following properties [24]

- $q_n(\alpha, \mu) \leq 1$ and $q_n(\alpha, \mu) \rightarrow 1$, where $\alpha \rightarrow 0$.
- $q_n(\alpha, \mu) \leq \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\alpha}} \mu^{-n}$
- $|q_n(\alpha, \mu) - 1| \leq \frac{\sqrt{\alpha}}{2} \mu^n$.

The properties of function (3.6) allow to insert it legibly into (2.7) for the parameter $\alpha > 0$, here μ is considered as a damping factor for the expression 3.7 which can be chosen by trial under the condition $\mu \geq \frac{R_1}{R_0}$. Thus, a new regularized scheme associated to the noisy data u_0^δ, u_1^δ can be constructed as

$$u_{\alpha, \mu}^\delta(r, \theta) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{\mu^{-2n}}{\alpha + \mu^{-2n}} (f_n^\delta(r) \cos(n\theta) + g_n^\delta(r) \sin(n\theta)) \tag{3.7}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} f_0^\delta(r) &= c_{0,1}^\delta + c_{0,2}^\delta \ln(r), & g_0^\delta(r) &= 0 \\ f_n^\delta(r) &= c_{n,1}^\delta r^{-n} + c_{n,2}^\delta r^n, & g_n^\delta(r) &= d_{n,1}^\delta r^{-n} + d_{n,2}^\delta r^n, \quad \text{pour } n \geq 1 \end{aligned} \tag{3.8}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} c_{0,1}^\delta &= A_0^\delta - A_0'^\delta R_0 \ln R_0, & d_{0,1}^\delta &= 0 \\ c_{0,2}^\delta &= A_0'^\delta R_0, & d_{0,2}^\delta &= 0 \\ c_{n,1}^\delta &= \frac{1}{2} A_n^\delta R_0^n - \frac{1}{2n} A_n'^\delta R_0^{n+1}, & d_{n,1}^\delta &= \frac{1}{2} B_n^\delta R_0^n - \frac{1}{2n} B_n'^\delta R_0^{n+1} \quad n \geq 1 \\ c_{n,2}^\delta &= \frac{1}{2} A_n^\delta R_0^{-n} + \frac{1}{2n} A_n'^\delta R_0^{1-n}, & d_{n,2}^\delta &= \frac{1}{2} B_n^\delta R_0^{-n} + \frac{1}{2n} B_n'^\delta R_0^{1-n} \quad n \geq 1 \end{aligned} \tag{3.9}$$

It can be seen that $\Delta(f_n(r) \cos(n\theta)) = \Delta(g_n(r) \sin(n\theta)) = 0$, for $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Therefore $\Delta u_{\alpha, \mu}^\delta = 0$, thus $u_{\alpha, \mu}^\delta$ provide a solution to the equation (3.2) and the following convergence can be obtained

$$u_{\alpha,\mu}(r, \theta) \rightarrow u(r, \theta), \quad \text{where } \alpha \rightarrow 0,$$

$$\frac{\partial u_{\alpha,\mu}}{\partial n}(r, \theta) \rightarrow \frac{\partial u}{\partial n}(r, \theta), \quad \text{where } \alpha \rightarrow 0.$$

Convergence estimates under exact data

Lemma (i): Let $u_0, u_1 \in L^2(\Gamma_0)$, for $\mu \geq \frac{R_1}{R_0}$, $\alpha > 0$ then $\|u_{\alpha,\mu}(r, \cdot)\|$ is bounded.

Proof. Let $u_{\alpha,\mu}$ is given by (3.7) then from (2.12) we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \|u_{\alpha,\mu}(r, \cdot)\|^2 &= 2\pi q_0(\alpha, \mu)^2 f_0(r)^2 + \pi \sum_{n \geq 1} q_n(\alpha, \mu)^2 (f_n(r)^2 + g_n(r)^2) \\ &\leq \frac{\pi}{2\alpha} f_0(r)^2 + \frac{\pi}{4\alpha} \sum_{n \geq 1} \mu^{-2n} (f_n(r)^2 + g_n(r)^2) \\ &\leq \frac{\pi}{\alpha} \left(A_0^2 + A_0'^2 R_0^2 \left(\ln \frac{R_1}{R_0} \right)^2 \right) + \frac{\pi}{\alpha} \sum_{n \geq 1} (A_n^2 + B_n^2 + R_0^2 A_n'^2 + R_0^2 B_n'^2) \\ &\leq \frac{2\pi}{\alpha} C_0^2 (A_0^2 + A_0'^2) + \frac{\pi}{\alpha} C_1^2 \sum_{n \geq 1} (A_n^2 + B_n^2 + A_n'^2 + B_n'^2) \end{aligned}$$

where $C_0^2 = \max \left\{ \frac{R_0^2}{2} \left(\ln \frac{R_1}{R_0} \right)^2, 1 \right\}$ and $C_1^2 = \max \{1, R_0^2\}$ are positive constant. By taking $C_2^2 = \max \{C_0^2, C_1^2\}$ we obtain that

$$\|u_{\alpha,\mu}(r, \cdot)\| \leq \frac{C_2}{\sqrt{\alpha}} (\|u_0\|^2 + \|u_1\|^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

Lemma (ii). If $\|u(r, \cdot)\|$ is bounded and $\mu \geq \frac{R_1}{R_0}$, then $u_{\alpha,\mu}$ converge to u as α tends to zero.

Proof. According to the property $\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 0} q_n(\cdot, \cdot) = 1$, therefore $\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 0} u_{\alpha,\mu} = u$. Using the limit definition then:

$\forall \epsilon > 0, \exists \alpha_0 > 0$, for $0 < \alpha \leq \alpha_0$, we have that $|q_n(\alpha, \mu) - 1| < \epsilon$. We can choose that $\epsilon = \frac{\sqrt{\alpha}}{\mu^n}$, where there exists $\alpha_0(n)$, such as $0 < \alpha \leq \alpha_0(n)$, for $\alpha_0(n) \leq \sup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \alpha_0(n) = \alpha_0$, then from the lemma (i) we have the estimation

$$\begin{aligned} \|u_{\alpha,\mu}(r, \cdot) - u(r, \cdot)\|^2 &= 2\pi (q_0(\alpha, \mu) - 1)^2 f_0(r)^2 + \pi \sum_{n \geq 0} (q_n(\alpha, \mu) - 1)^2 (f_n(r)^2 + g_n(r)^2) \\ &\leq 2\pi \alpha C_0^2 (A_0^2 + A_0'^2) + \pi \alpha C_1^2 \sum_{n \geq 1} (A_n^2 + B_n^2 + A_n'^2 + B_n'^2) \end{aligned}$$

where $C_0^2 = \max \left\{ \frac{R_0^2}{2} \left(\ln \frac{R_1}{R_0} \right)^2, 1 \right\}$ and $C_1^2 = \max \{1, R_0^2\}$ are positive constant. By taking $C_2^2 = \max \{C_0^2, C_1^2\}$ we obtain that

$$\|u_{\alpha,\mu}(r, \cdot) - u(r, \cdot)\| \leq C_2 \sqrt{\alpha} \left(\|u_0\|^2 + \|u_1\|^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \rightarrow 0, \text{ where } \alpha \rightarrow 0$$

Lemma (iii): Let $\{u_0, u_1\} \in L^2(\Gamma_0)$, the following norms $\|u_{\alpha,\mu}(R_0, \cdot) - u_0\|_{L^2(\Gamma_0)}$, $\|\frac{\partial u_{\alpha,\mu}}{\partial n}(R_0, \cdot) - u_1\|_{L^2(\Gamma_0)}$ converges to zero when $\alpha \rightarrow 0$.

Proof. The effect that $\mu \geq \frac{R_1}{R_0}$, from the property (2.12) we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \|u_{\alpha,\mu}(R_0, \cdot) - u_0\|^2 &= \left\| \sum_{n \geq 0} q_n(\alpha, \mu) [f_n(R_0) \cos(n\theta) + g_n(R_0) \sin(n\theta)] - u_0 \right\|^2 \\ &= \left\| \sum_{n \geq 0} [q_n(\alpha, \mu) - 1] [f_n(R_0) \cos(n\theta) + g_n(R_0) \sin(n\theta)] \right\|^2 \\ &= 2\pi (q_0(\alpha, \mu) - 1)^2 f_0(R_0)^2 + \pi \sum_{n \geq 0} (q_n(\alpha, \mu) - 1)^2 (f_n(R_0)^2 + g_n(R_0)^2) \\ &\leq \frac{\alpha}{4} \|u_0\|^2 \rightarrow 0, \text{ as, } \alpha \rightarrow 0. \end{aligned}$$

In the same way

$$\begin{aligned} \left\| \frac{\partial u_{\alpha,\mu}}{\partial n}(R_0, \cdot) - u_1 \right\|^2 &= \left\| \sum_{n \geq 0} q_n(\alpha, \mu) \left[\frac{\partial f_n}{\partial r}(R_0) \cos(n\theta) + \frac{\partial g_n}{\partial r}(R_0) \sin(n\theta) \right] - u_1 \right\|^2 \\ &\leq \frac{\alpha}{4} \|u_1\|^2 \rightarrow 0, \text{ as, } \alpha \rightarrow 0. \end{aligned}$$

Error estimate under noisy data

Lemma (Uniqueness of solution) (iv): For all noisy data $\{u_0^\delta, u_1^\delta\} \in L^2(\Gamma_0)$ the function given by (3.7) is the unique solution to the problem (3.2)-(3.3)-(3.4) and it's continuously dependent on u_0^δ, u_1^δ .

Proof. Let $u_{\alpha_1}^\delta, u_{\alpha_2}^\delta$ be two solutions to the problem (3.2)-(3.3)-(3.4), which is corresponding to the given data (u_0^δ, u_1^δ) , (v_0^δ, v_1^δ) , respectively, given as

$$\begin{aligned} u_{\alpha,\mu}^\delta(r, \theta) &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{\mu^{-2n}}{\alpha + \mu^{-2n}} (f_n^\delta(r) \cos(n\theta) + g_n^\delta(r) \sin(n\theta)) \\ u_{\alpha,\mu}^\delta(r, \theta) &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{\mu^{-2n}}{\alpha + \mu^{-2n}} (h_n^\delta(r) \cos(n\theta) + d_n^\delta(r) \sin(n\theta)) \end{aligned}$$

For $\mu \geq \frac{R_1}{R_0}$ and from the lemma (i) we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \|u_{\alpha_1}^\delta(r, \theta) - u_{\alpha_2}^\delta(r, \theta)\|^2 &= \left\| \sum_{n \geq 0} q_n(\alpha, \mu) [(f_n^\delta(r) - h_n^\delta(r)) \cos(n\theta) + (g_n^\delta(r) - d_n^\delta(r)) \sin(n\theta)] \right\|^2 \\ &\leq \frac{\pi}{2\alpha} (f_0^\delta(r) - h_0^\delta(r))^2 + \frac{\pi}{4\alpha} \sum_{n \geq 1} \mu^{-2n} ((f_n^\delta(r) - h_n^\delta(r))^2 + (g_n^\delta(r) - d_n^\delta(r))^2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\leq \frac{C_2^2}{\alpha} (\|v_0^\delta - u_0^\delta\|^2 + \|v_1^\delta - u_1^\delta\|^2)$$

$$\leq \frac{2^3 C_2^2 \delta^2}{\alpha} \rightarrow 0, \text{ when, } \delta \rightarrow 0$$

where $C_0^2 = \max \left\{ \frac{R_0^2}{2} \left(\ln \frac{R_1}{R_0} \right)^2, 1 \right\}$, $C_1^2 = \max \{1, R_0^2\}$ and $C_2^2 = \max \{C_0^2, C_1^2\}$ are a positive constants.

Theorem: If $\|u(r, \cdot)\|$ is bounded and $\mu \geq \frac{R_1}{R_0}$, then $u_{\alpha, \mu}^\delta$ converge to u as δ tends to zero.

Proof. We have that

$$\|u_{\alpha, \mu}^\delta(r, \theta) - u(r, \theta)\| \leq \|u_{\alpha, \mu}^\delta(r, \theta) - u_{\alpha, \mu}(r, \theta)\| + \|u_{\alpha, \mu}(r, \theta) - u(r, \theta)\|$$

$$\leq \|u_{\alpha, \mu}^\delta(r, \theta) - u_{\alpha, \mu}(r, \theta)\| + C_2 \sqrt{\alpha} (\|u_0\|^2 + \|u_1\|^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

where $C_0^2 = \max \left\{ \frac{R_0^2}{2} \left(\ln \frac{R_1}{R_0} \right)^2, 1 \right\}$, $C_1^2 = \max \{1, R_0^2\}$ and $C_2^2 = \max \{C_0^2, C_1^2\}$ are a positive constants given in

lemma (i) From the property (i) and the lemma (iv) we obtain that

$$\|u_{\alpha, \mu}^\delta(r, \theta) - u_{\alpha, \mu}(r, \theta)\|^2 = \left\| \sum_{n \geq 0} q_n(\alpha, \mu) [(f_n^\delta(r) - f_n(r)) \cos(n\theta) + (g_n^\delta(r) - g_n(r)) \sin(n\theta)] \right\|^2$$

$$\leq \frac{\pi}{2\alpha} (f_0^\delta(r) - f_0(r))^2 + \frac{\pi}{4\alpha} \sum_{n \geq 1} \mu^{-2n} ((f_n^\delta(r) - f_n(r))^2 + (g_n^\delta(r) - g_n(r))^2)$$

$$\leq \frac{C_2^2}{\alpha} (\|u_0^\delta - u_0\|^2 + \|u_1^\delta - u_1\|^2) \leq \frac{2C_2^2 \delta^2}{\alpha}$$

Then

$$\|u_{\alpha, \mu}^\delta(r, \theta) - u_{\alpha, \mu}(r, \theta)\| \leq \frac{\sqrt{2} C_2}{\sqrt{\alpha}} \delta$$

Therefore

$$\|u_{\alpha, \mu}^\delta(r, \theta) - u(r, \theta)\| \leq \frac{\sqrt{2} C_2}{\sqrt{\alpha}} \delta + C_2 \sqrt{\alpha} (\|u_0\|^2 + \|u_1\|^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

take $\alpha(\delta) = C_3 \delta$, where C_3 is a constant to be determined, then we obtain that

$$\|u_{\alpha, \mu}^\delta(r, \theta) - u(r, \theta)\| \leq C_2 \left(\sqrt{C_3} (\|u_0\|^2 + \|u_1\|^2)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{C_3}} \right) \sqrt{\delta} \rightarrow 0, \text{ as } \delta \rightarrow 0.$$

COLLOCATION METHOD

In the conventional Trefftz method, the numerical solution for the two-dimensional Laplace equation in doubly-connected planar domain is expressed by linear summation of the following bases [3,22,24].

$$\{1, \ln r, r^{\pm n} \cos(n\theta), r^{\pm n} \sin(n\theta), n = 1, 2, \dots\} \tag{4.1}$$

Recently, Liu [19,23,16] had modified the T-complete functions in (4.1) by considering the characteristic length of the computational domain to stabilize the numerical scheme,

$$\left\{ 1, \ln r, \left(\frac{r}{R_1}\right)^n \cos(n\theta), \left(\frac{R_0}{r}\right)^n \cos(n\theta), \left(\frac{r}{R_1}\right)^n \sin(n\theta), \left(\frac{R_0}{r}\right)^n \sin(n\theta), n = 1, 2, \dots \right\} \tag{4.2}$$

Our starting point in equation (2.8) is inserting the damping function noted $q_n(\alpha, \mu)$ for a choice of regularisation parameter $\alpha > 0$ and the damping factor must be chosen in relation to the characteristic length of the computational domain,

in such way that $\mu \geq \frac{R_1}{R_0}$. Therefore the new set of T-complete functions is defined as follows:

$$\{q_0(\alpha, \mu), q_0(\alpha, \mu) \ln r, q_n(\alpha, \mu) r^{\pm n} \cos(n\theta), q_n(\alpha, \mu) r^{\pm n} \sin(n\theta), n = 1, 2, \dots\} \tag{4.3}$$

In the NRCTM, we approximate the regularized scheme (3.7) by a linear combination of T-complete functions (4.3) given on the form of admissible functions in finite term with regularized parameter α and a damping factor μ as:

$$u_{\alpha, \mu}(r, \theta) = \sum_{n=0}^m q_n(\alpha, \mu) (f_n(r) \cos(n\theta) + g_n(r) \sin(n\theta)) \tag{4.4}$$

It is known that collocation method has a great advantage to be applied on different geometric shapes, and the simplicity for computer programming. In order to apply the collocation method, we define θ_i as the collocated points on Γ_0 given by

$$\theta_i = ih, \quad \text{for } i = 0, \dots, m, \quad \text{and,} \quad h = \frac{2\pi}{m+1}. \tag{4.5}$$

In Eq. (4.4) there are $4m + 2$ unknown coefficients, can be obtained by imposing the different collocated points (4.5) in (2.6) for $i = 1, \dots, 2m + 1$

$$\sum_{n=0}^m q_n(\alpha, \mu) (f_n(R_0) \cos(n\theta_i) + g_n(R_0) \sin(n\theta_i)) = u_0(\theta_i) \tag{4.6}$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^m q_n(\alpha, \mu) (f'_n(R_0) \cos(n\theta_i) + g'_n(R_0) \sin(n\theta_i)) = u_1(\theta_i) \tag{4.7}$$

we obtain a linear equations system with dimensions $n = 4m + 2$ denoted by:

$$Ax = b \tag{4.8}$$

where the matrix $A \in \mathbb{R}^{4m+2} \times \mathbb{R}^{4m+2}$ is given by

$$\begin{bmatrix}
 q_0 & q_0 \ln(R_0) & q_1 R_0 \cos \theta_0 & q_1 R_0^{-1} \cos \theta_0 & q_1 R_0 \sin \theta_0 & q_1 R_0^{-1} \sin \theta_0 & \cdots \\
 0 & \frac{q_0}{R_0} & q_1 \cos \theta_0 & -q_1 R_0^{-2} \cos \theta_0 & q_1 \sin \theta_0 & -q_1 R_0^{-2} \sin \theta_0 & \cdots \\
 q_0 & q_0 \ln(R_0) & q_1 R_0 \cos \theta_1 & q_1 R_0^{-1} \cos \theta_1 & q_1 R_0 \sin \theta_1 & q_1 R_0^{-1} \sin \theta_1 & \cdots \\
 0 & \frac{q_0}{R_0} & q_1 \cos \theta_1 & -q_1 R_0^{-2} \cos \theta_1 & q_1 \sin \theta_1 & -q_1 R_0^{-2} \sin \theta_1 & \cdots \\
 \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\
 q_0 & q_0 \ln(R_0) & q_1 R_0 \cos \theta_m & q_1 R_0^{-1} \cos \theta_m & q_1 R_0 \sin \theta_m & q_1 R_0^{-1} \sin \theta_m & \cdots \\
 0 & \frac{q_0}{R_0} & q_1 \cos \theta_m & -q_1 R_0^{-2} \cos \theta_m & q_1 \sin \theta_m & -q_1 R_0^{-2} \sin \theta_m & \cdots
 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.9)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix}
 \cdots & q_m R_0^m \cos \theta_0 & q_m R_0^{-m} \cos \theta_0 & q_m R_0^m \sin \theta_0 & q_m R_0^{-m} \sin \theta_0 \\
 \cdots & m q_m R_0^{m-1} \cos \theta_0 & -m q_m R_0^{-m-1} \cos \theta_0 & m q_m R_0^{m-1} \sin \theta_0 & -m q_m R_0^{-m-1} \sin \theta_0 \\
 \cdots & q_m R_0^m \cos \theta_1 & q_m R_0^{-m} \cos \theta_1 & q_m R_0^m \sin \theta_1 & q_m R_0^{-m} \sin \theta_1 \\
 \cdots & m q_m R_0^{m-1} \cos \theta_1 & -m q_m R_0^{-m-1} \cos \theta_1 & m q_m R_0^{m-1} \sin \theta_1 & -m q_m R_0^{-m-1} \sin \theta_1 \\
 \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\
 \cdots & q_m R_0^m \cos \theta_m & q_m R_0^{-m} \cos \theta_m & q_m R_0^m \sin \theta_m & q_m R_0^{-m} \sin \theta_m \\
 \cdots & m q_m R_0^{m-1} \cos \theta_m & -m q_m R_0^{-m-1} \cos \theta_m & m q_m R_0^{m-1} \sin \theta_m & -m q_m R_0^{-m-1} \sin \theta_m
 \end{bmatrix}$$

and

$$x = [c_{0,1}, c_{0,2}, c_{1,1}, c_{1,2}, d_{1,1}, d_{1,2}, \dots, c_{m,1}, c_{m,2}, d_{m,1}, d_{m,2}] \in \mathbb{R}^{4m+2} \quad (4.10)$$

$$b = [u_0(\theta_0), u_1(\theta_0), u_0(\theta_1), u_1(\theta_1), \dots, u_0(\theta_{2m}), u_1(\theta_{2m})] \in \mathbb{R}^{4m+2} \quad (4.11)$$

The conjugate gradient method can be used to solve the following normal equation:

$$A^T A x = A^T b \quad (4.12)$$

By inserting the calculated x into Eq. (4.8), thus we find a semi-analytical solution for $u_{\alpha}^{\delta}(r, \theta)$ as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_{\alpha, \mu}^{\delta}(r, \theta) = & q_0(\alpha, \mu)(x_0 + x_1 \ln(r)) + \sum_{n=1}^m q_n(\alpha, \mu)(x_{4n-2} r^{-n} + x_{4n-1} r^n) \cos(n\theta) \\
 & + \sum_{n=1}^m q_n(\alpha, \mu)(x_{4n} r^{-n} + x_{4n+1} r^n) \sin(n\theta)
 \end{aligned} \quad (4.13)$$

where $x = (x_0, x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, \dots, x_{4m+1}) \in \mathbb{R}^{4m+2}$ are the components of x .

NUMERICAL TEST

In order to test numerical stability of the NRCTM, the parameter α and the damping factor $\mu \geq \frac{R_1}{R_0}$ are chosen by trial and error. In the following examples we give a simple exact solution u for the equation (2.1) and we verify the boundary condition

(2.2)-(2.3), we consider the approximate solution which corresponds to the data with and without noise (see section 4), we show the comparison between this one with the MCTM. Here we consider an annulus domain with radius R_0 and R_1 . The solution of Eq. (4.12) is obtained under a stopping criterion 10^{-15} . The noisy data (3.1) has been generated with noise added to the Dirichlet-Neumann data in the form.

$$u_0^\delta = u_0 + \epsilon \frac{\|u_0\|_{L^2}}{\|\xi\|_{L^2}} \xi, \quad u_1^\delta = u_1 + \epsilon \frac{\|u_1\|_{L^2}}{\|\xi\|_{L^2}} \xi \tag{5.1}$$

where ξ is a normally distributed random variable and ϵ is the relative noisy level. In our algorithm, we note with **Error_u** the evaluate relative error between the exact solution u , and its computed approximations $u_{\alpha,\mu}^\delta$, and can be given in the sense of Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) by

$$Error_u = \frac{\|u_{\alpha,\mu}^\delta - u\|_{L^2}}{\|u\|_{L^2}} \tag{5.2}$$

with $R_0 \leq r \leq R_1$, and using the collocate points θ_i given in (4.5).

Example 7.1

We start with a simple example of an annulus defined by the radius $R_0 = \frac{1}{2}$, $R_1 = 1$, and we consider the exact solution given by

$$u(r, \theta) = x^2 - y^2 = r^2 \cos 2\theta \tag{5.3}$$

Therefore, the data on the circle with a radius $R_0 = \frac{1}{2}$ are given by

$$u_0(\theta) = R_0^2 \cos 2\theta, \quad 0 \leq \theta \leq 2\pi \tag{5.4}$$

$$u_1(\theta) = 2R_0 \cos 2\theta, \quad 0 \leq \theta \leq 2\pi \tag{5.5}$$

We solve this problem by the new regularized collocation Trefftz method NRCTM presented in Section 4, whose the results along a unit circle $r = 1$ are shown by chosen the damping factor as $\mu = 2$.

In 7.1 we show the comparisons between the exact solution u , and its computed approximations by using the MCTM and the NRCTM, without noise, the errors was plotted in 7.1, respectively with regularization parameter chosen by the trial as $\alpha = 0.1$ for $m = 40$.

Figures 1,2: For Example 7.1. Comparing the exact solution and numerical solutions without noise, in (5.1), and the numerical errors are plotted in (5.1). For $m = 40$, $\alpha = 0.1$.

We can compare the NRCTM and MCTM on this example with very high accuracy, as shown in 7.1 respectively, for the cases $m = 5; 10; 40; 120$ with a regularized parameter chosen by trial as $\alpha = 10^{-2}, 10^{-1}, 10^{-1}, 10^{-1}$, respectively. It can be seen that by the NRCTM the error decreases when m increases, but this is contrary by the MCTM.

Figure 3: Errors under MCTM.

Figure 4: Errors under NRCTM.

Figures 3,4: Plotting the numerical errors for example 5.1.

In 7.1 we compare the exact solution with the numerical solutions by using the NRCTM under the noises $\epsilon = 0.01$ and 0.1 , the corresponding errors was plotted in 7.1, the regularization parameter was chosen by trial and error by $\alpha = 10^{-6}$ and 10^{-5} respectively, with truncation number $m = 70$. It can be seen that the numerical solutions are close to the exact solution, which indicates that the present method is robust against the noise, and even whose level was taken up to 1% (0.01) and 10% (0.1), the numerical error was still with an L^2 error smaller than 0.8% (0.008) and 5% (0.05) respectively.

Figure 5,6: For example 7.1. Exact solution and numerical solution by NRCTM with noises in (5.1), the numerical errors are plotted in (5.1). For $m = 70$, $\alpha(0.01) = 10^{-6}$ and $\alpha(0.1) = 10^{-5}$

Example 5.2 Next, we consider $R_0 = 1$, $R_1 = 3$, and the damping factor is chosen by $\mu = 5$. Let the following harmonic function be an exact solution to our problem, given by

$$u(r, \theta) = -r^3 \sin 3\theta + r^2 \cos 2\theta \tag{5.6}$$

Therefore, the data on the circle with a radius $R_0 = 1$ are given by

$$u_0(\theta) = -R_0^3 \sin 3\theta + R_0^2 \cos 2\theta, \quad 0 \leq \theta \leq 2\pi \tag{5.7}$$

$$u_1(\theta) = -3R_0^2 \sin 3\theta + 2R_0 \cos 2\theta, \quad 0 \leq \theta \leq 2\pi \tag{5.8}$$

We solve this problem by the NRCTM, whose result along a circle with the radius $R_1 = 3$ and the damping factor is chosen by $\mu = 5$.

In 7.2 we show the comparisons between the exact solution u , and its computed approximations by using the MCTM and the NRCTM, without noise, the errors was plotted in 7.2, respectively with regularization parameter chosen by the trial as 0.1 for $m = 80$.

Figures 7,8: For Example 7.2. Comparing the exact solution and numerical solutions without noise, in (5.2), and the numerical errors are plotted in (5.2). For $m = 80$, $\alpha = 0.1$.

We can compare the NRCTM and MCTM on this example with very high accuracy, as shown in 5.2 respectively, for the cases $m = 4; 20; 50; 150$ with a regularized parameter chosen by trial as $\alpha = 10^{-2}, 10^{-6}, 10^{-6}, 10^{-2}$, respectively. It can be seen that by the NRCTM the error decreases when m increases, on the contrary in the MCTM.

Figure 9: Errors under MCTM.

Figure 10: Errors under NRCTM.

Figures 9,10: Plotting the numerical errors for example 7.2.

In 7.2 we compare the exact solution with the numerical solutions by using the NRCTM under the noises $\epsilon = 0.01$ and 0.07 , the corresponding errors was plottedd in 7.2, the regularization parameter was chosen by trial and error by $\alpha = 0.5$ and 0.1 respectively, with truncation number $m = 50$. It can be seen that the numerical solutions are close to the exact solution, which indicates that the present method is robust against the noise, and even whose level was taken up to 1% (0.01) and 7% (0.07), the numerical error was still with an L^2 error smaller than 2% (0.02) and 8% (0.08) respectively.

Figures 10 a,b: For example 7.2. Exact solution and numerical solution by NRCTM with noises in (5.2), the numerical errors are plotted in (5.2). For $m = 50$, $\alpha(0.01) = 0.5$ and $\alpha(0.07) = 0.1$

Example 7.3

For this example the domain is considered between the radius $R_0 = 2$ and $R_1 = 5$, the damping factor is chosen by $\mu = 4$. To illustrate the accuracy and stability of the new method we consider the following analytical solution

$$u(r, \theta) = \cos x \cosh y + \sin x \cosh y.$$

The exact boundary data can be derived as:

$$u_0(\theta) = \cos(R_0 \cos \theta) \cosh(R_0 \sin \theta) + \sin(R_0 \cos \theta) \cosh(R_0 \sin \theta)$$

$$u_1(\theta) = -\cos \theta \sin(R_0 \cos \theta) \cosh(R_0 \sin \theta) + \sin \theta \cos(R_0 \cos \theta) \sinh(R_0 \sin \theta) + \cos \theta \cos(R_0 \cos \theta) \sinh(R_0 \sin \theta) + \sin \theta \sin(R_0 \cos \theta) \cosh(R_0 \sin \theta)$$

We apply the NRCTM on this example as was done in examples 1 and 2. In 7.3 we show the comparisons between the exact solution u , and its computed approximations by using the MCTM and the NRCTM, without noise, the errors was plotted in 7.3, respectively with regularization parameter chosen by the trial as 10^{-9} for $m = 30$.

Figure 11

Figure 12

Figures 11,12: For Example 7.3. Comparing the exact solution and numerical solutions without noise, in (5.3), and the numerical errors are plotted in (5.3). For $m = 30$, $\alpha = 10^{-9}$.

The result is accurate by using the NRCTM as shown in 7.3, where $m = 60$, the regularization parameter for the numerical

reconstruction is $\alpha = 10^{-9}$ and $\alpha = 10^{-1}$ for noisy data with $\epsilon = 0.08$. The boundary data $g(\theta)$ as shown in 7.3 were plotted for the circle with radius $R = 5$, and the errors were plotted in 7.3. Also, it can be seen that in 7.3 the errors are larger than in 7.3 when the truncation number changes from $m = 30$ to $m = 60$, respectively.

Figure 13

Figure 14

Figures 13,14: For example 7.3. Exact solution and numerical solution by NRCTM with and without noises in (5.3), the numerical errors are plotted in (5.3). For $m = 60$, $\alpha = 10^{-9}$ and $\alpha(0.08) = 0.1$.

We can summarize that the numerical experiments show satisfactory reconstructions for the function u also with reasonable stability against noisy data. By comparing errors, we can note, the quality of the reconstructions in the case of the MCTM is not as accurate as in the NRCTM.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have employed a Tikhonov's damping factor to construct a new regularized Trefftz method for solving an ill-posed inverse problem for the Laplacian. The given data on the accessible curve are assumed to have a Fourier expansions. The convergence and stability estimates have been obtained under a priori assumption for the exact solution.

In the numerical aspect, a linear system equations is obtained, we solve the direct problem by the conjugate gradient method as precise as possible, to determine the coefficients and this provide us a semi-analytical solution without needing for any iteration, however, the inverse problem need to collocate a less precise data than the given one and the parameters was chosen by trial provide us a tool for minimizing the errors.

This new method was found it to be effective and stable even for a great of truncation number compared with the modified collocation Trefftz method, some numerical tests had given to show its effectiveness and stability. More importantly, here we only considered the ill-posed problem in an annulus with circular boundaries, this new method can be extended to other problems in a more complex domain.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict interests.

Authors' Contributions

The authors conceived of the presented method. Both authors developed the analytic approach and performed the numerical simulations. All authors discussed the results and contributed to the final manuscript.

Availability of Data

Not applicable.

REFERENCES

1. Liu CS. A highly accurate collocation Trefftz method for solving the Laplace equation in the doubly connected domains. *Numeric Meth Part diff Eq.* 2008;24(1):179-192. doi: 10.1002/num.20257.
2. Ramm AG. A geometrical inverse problem. *Inv Prob.* 1986;2(2):19.
3. Karageorghis A, Lesnic D, Marin L. Regularized collocation Trefftz method for void detection in two-dimensional steady-state heat conduction problems. In *Pres in Sc and Engine.* 2014;22(3):95-418.
4. Liu CS. A highly accurate MCTM for direct and inverse problems of biharmonic equation in arbitrary plane domains. *CMES.* 2008;30(2):65-75. <https://bit.ly/3MbKoFq>
5. Kirsch A. *An Introduction to the mathematical theory of inverse problems.* Springer. 2011.
6. Ott KA, Brown RM. The mixed problem for the Laplacian in Lipschitz domains. *Potential Anal.* 2013;38:1333-1364. <https://bit.ly/3McyU4E>
7. Lanzani L, Capogna L, Brown RM. The mixed problem in L for some two-dimensional Lipschitz domains. *Math Ann.* 2008;342:91-124.
8. Lanzani L, Capogna L, Brown RM. The solution of mixed boundary value problem for the Laplace equation in a multiply connected domain. *Probl Anal Issues Anal.* 2019;26(2):51-66.
9. Kress R. *Linear Integral Equations.* Springer. 2014.
10. Hadamard J. *Lecture note on Cauchy's problem in linear partial differential equations.* Yale University Press; 1923.
11. Tajani C, Abouchabaka J. On the data completion problem for Laplace's equation. *Annals of the Univ of Cra, Math and Comp Sci Ser.* 2018;45(1):11-36. <https://bit.ly/3wn7Rgj>
12. Hadj A, Saker H. Integral equations method for solving a Biharmonic inverse problem in detection of Robin coefficients. *Applied Numerical Mathematics.* 2021;160:436-450. doi: 10.1016/j.apnum.2020.10.005
13. Ausaru A, Nagarani P. Effect of external body acceleration on solute dispersion in unsteady non-newtonian fluid flow-the generalized dispersion model approach. *Int J Appl Comput Math.* 2022;8:13. doi: 10.1007/s40819-021-01209-w.
14. Li ZC, Lu TT, Huang HT, Cheng AHD. Trefftz, collocation, and other boundary methods - A comparison. *Numeric Meths for Part Diff Eq.* 2008;23(1):93-144. doi: 10.1002/num.20159.
15. Chen CT, Chen KH, Lee JF, Chen JT. Adaptive error estimation of the Trefftz method for solving the Cauchy problem. *WIT Press.* 2007;44:14. doi: 10.2495/BE070051.
16. Liu CS. A modified Trefftz Method for Two-Dimensional Laplace Equation considering the domain's characteristic length. *CMES.* 2007;21(1):53-65. doi: 10.3970/cmcs.2007.021.053.
17. Liu CS. A modified collocation Trefftz method for the inverse Cauchy problem of Laplace equation. *Engine anal with Bound elem.* 2008;32(9):778-785.
18. Karageorghis A. Efficient Trefftz collocation algorithms for elliptic problems in circular domains. *Numer Algor.* 2013;64:427-453. doi: 10.1007/s11075-012-9673-8.
19. Liu CS. Solving the inverse problems of Laplace equation to determine the robin coefficient cracks position inside a disk. *CMES.* 2009;40(1):1-28 .
20. Liu CS, Wang F, Gu Y. Trefftz energy method for solving the Cauchy problem of the Laplace equation. *App Math Lets.* 2018;79:187-195.
21. Fan CM, Chan HF. Modified collocation Trefftz method for geometry boundary identification problem of heat conduction. *Numerical Heat Transfer.* 2011;59(1):58-75. doi: 10.1080/10407790.2010.541355.
22. Kita E, Kamiya N. Trefftz method: An overview. *Adv Eng Software.* 1995;24(1):3-12.
23. Yeih W, Liu CS, Kuo CL, Atluri SN. On solving the direct/inverse cauchy problems of Laplace equation in a multiply connected domain, using the generalized multiple-source-point boundary-collocation Trefftz Method and characteristic lengths. *Computers, Materials & Continua.* 2010;17(3):275-302. doi: 10.3970/cmc.2010.017.275.
24. Thirumaran V, Weliwita JA, Ishak MIM. An Analysis of axial couette flow in annular region of abruptly stopped pipes. *Phy Sci Inter Jour.* 2018;17(4):1-12. doi: 10.9734/PSIJ/2018/40076.
25. Benrabah A, Boussetila N. Modified nonlocal boundary value problem method for an ill-posed problem for the biharmonic equation. *Inv Probs in Sci and Engi.* 2018;340-368. doi: 10.1080/17415977.2018.1461859.

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